

Supplemented material to “Impact of Titanium on the Catalytic Activity of Zn-BDC and Cu-BDC Thin Films in the Photoreduction of CO₂”

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This is the supplementary material to the publication “Impact of Titanium on the Catalytic Activity of Zn-BDC and Cu-BDC Thin Films in the Photoreduction of CO₂”.

The thin films were synthesized using an aerosol-assisted chemical vapor deposition (AACVD) system with precursor solutions in the spray system.

Figure S1. Vertical flow chemical vapor assisted thin film deposition system and dual sphere fogging.

The reaction system used an artificial light lamp that was characterized to know its emission wavelengths (white light with wavelengths $\sim \lambda = 436 \text{ nm}$, $\sim \lambda = 405 \text{ nm}$ and $\sim \lambda = 365 \text{ nm}$).

Figure S2. Lamp emission spectrum of the reaction system.

The following sample preparation was used for the titration of the reaction products:

- Collection of samples from the liquid in the photoreactor.
- Filter the samples with a 0.45 μm filter to remove suspended solids that may clog the column.
- Prepare an aqueous solution acidulated with H_2SO_4 at 0.05% v/v.
- Degas the mobile phase by ultrasonication to avoid bubble formation during analysis.
- Hydrophilic interaction column (HILIC), dimensions 150 mm length, 4.6 mm internal diameter, particle size 5 μm . Column temperature at 25°C.
- Refractive index (RI) detector, adjusting the detector sensitivity to ensure detection of compounds at low concentrations. Calibrate the detector according to the manufacturer's manual.
- Run Protocol: Allow the column to reach equilibrium with the mobile phase for at least 30 minutes before the first injection. Mobile Phase Flow Rate: 1.0 mL/min, Injection Volume: 20 μL of the filtered sample.
- Elution Gradient: Use an isocratic gradient with the acidified aqueous solution (H_2SO_4 at 0.05 % v/v).